

ESSENCE OF CLUSTER APPROACH IN ORGANIZING STUDENT INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In order for students to activate the process of independent learning, it is necessary to form such characteristics as enthusiasm for independent learning, skills and abilities of independent learning, and the ability to learn independently.*

The article talks about the correct organization of the cluster approach to the implementation of independent education of students, the institutions that are part of the cluster, and the main motives for independent education.

Keywords: *institution, activity, interest, motive, need, opportunity, efficiency, quality.*

Introduction

In the activities of the cluster approach, resources are combined, and a common material base allows all participants of the educational process (children, parents, teachers) to use equipment, space, consulting support and other resources that are not available in a separate institution. A single developing field that includes all links and levels of education, as well as active network cooperation within it, increases the efficiency of each cluster member and allows full use of its creative potential.

Organizational and technological solutions of regulatory documents are an important condition for the correct organization of the cluster approach in the organization of independent education of students. Higher education institutions, lyceums, kindergartens, general education institutions, medical institutions and others can be included in the educational institutions operating in the cluster. The content of the educational cluster is determined by the main directions of activity, and their selection is determined by the constant monitoring of the needs and opportunities of the participants of the educational cluster. The effectiveness of the activity is checked by the qualitative diagnosis, the level of provision of resources (material, methodological, personnel) of the institutions that are part of the cluster.

It should be noted that effective use of financial resources is ensured within the cluster, because one of the conditions of cluster activity is corporate management, including material and financial resources.

As a result of the implementation of the cluster approach to the organization of independent education of students, the following are distinguished as predicted social effects:

- development of social partnership;
- finding resources for innovative training, retraining and professional development of pedagogical personnel;
- obtaining qualitatively new results of education based on continuous development of the child;
- possibility to improve the general image of institutions.

The problems of organizing independent education in the continuing education system were studied in the research works of J. Tolipova, N. Khalilov and others [6, 8].

In the monograph "Professional formation of future teachers of vocational education" by teacher scientist N.A. Muslimov, special attention is paid to independent education of students. In it, the principles and organizational-methodical conditions of independent learning by students in acquiring knowledge, i.e. autodidactic (autodidactic-self-learning and autonomy) were studied [5]. According to N.A. Muslimov, "Independent education" means the organization of regular, independent and autonomous activities in accordance with the subjective purpose of the educational process for the development of concepts, skills and competencies of knowledge acquisition [5].

Method

Students determine the goals and tasks that make up the content of independent education, depending on the strength and motivational reasons that arouse interest in independent education.

This can be expressed as follows:

1. Political independent education, modern reality and the attitude towards them, which are considered important in conducting independent activities;
2. Professional independent education in the preparatory period aimed at carrying out activities in the chosen direction, mastering the student's independent education;
3. Independent education directed to further study of academic subjects, personal life plans, personal interest;
4. Independent education related to the development of one's talents and hobbies.
5. Independent education aimed at training one's own character (fair).

Psychologists L.M. Fridman and K.N. Volkov "All branches of psychology (general, social, differential psychology) are important for a teacher. But two branches of psychology, namely youth psychology and pedagogical psychology, are very important for the teacher in solving pedagogical problems," he writes [7].

The process of teaching independent thinking is a key part of independent education. With the problems of independent thinking, many psychologists, in particular Gamezo and others, have conducted research [1].

In order to activate the process of independent learning, it is necessary to form the following characteristics in students:

- enthusiasm for independent education (motivation);
- independent learning qualifications and skills;
- the ability to learn independently.

Factors that actively encourage independent education include:

- direct active interest in independent activity;
- motives of moral aesthetic and spiritual satisfaction.

The stages of development of knowledge needs are:

- the stage of elementary scientific research activities (formation of the need for external impressions);
- the stage of formation of the need to know the world;
- the stage of formation of the need for training as an activity of acquiring the method of knowing;
- the stage of formation of orientation towards the selection of knowledge needs;

- the stage of developing the need for independent education.

Especially the last stage is important for research work. Because the formation of the need for independent study is important for students to become mature, well-rounded, qualified specialists in their field. Independent learning and control in the educational system is one of the main factors of independent education. In order to acquire independent knowledge, first of all, it is necessary to form the need for independent work, free, creative activity in students [13].

Results and discussion

The essence of the cluster approach in the organization of independent education of students is an increase in the volume of scientific knowledge, an increase in the share of theoretical cases in science and its impact on production activities, a reduction in the time between scientific innovations and their application in practice, ensures the superiority of information, and the development of the future specialist's ability and desire to engage in independent educational activities causes the need. Independent education is of great importance at all stages of educational activity. These include: creating awareness problems; perform tasks of a problematic type; strengthening of acquired knowledge; use of previously acquired knowledge, development of skills and competences, etc. can be included.

It is in the process of independent acquisition of knowledge that the independence of a person is formed, which is carried out in solving complex tasks and problem situations and is the result of the development of the mechanisms of the internal self-management system of a person, including cognition and mental activity. Mental independence is an integral part of personal independence, which, in turn, forms the basis of the formation and manifestation of life activity, serves as a necessary condition for them.

In new social conditions, with the significant expansion of the information field, the emergence of new sources and information carriers, the conditions for obtaining knowledge have changed accordingly, the methodology and didactics of independent education have significantly developed, and it is also necessary to change the organizational and pedagogical conditions of the independent education process. It can be said that mastering the required amount of knowledge can be achieved through the individual's own activity, desire to learn, creative attitude to his work. The concepts of "independence" and "cognitive activity" are phenomena of the same order. Independence can be considered as an individual's identity, ability, as an indicator of human activity. Independence is the implementation of activities without the participation and help of outsiders, without external incentives. Independence is expressed in setting a task, working effectively, taking initiative in new situations. From the point of view of the cognitive process: control of attention, independence, logical arguments and decision-making are reflected in the choice of methods of activity, the objectivity of self-evaluation is included in the concept of "independent cognition". The development of students' cognitive abilities takes place in the process of independent work, it helps to form practical skills and competencies, and helps to master the acquired knowledge.

One of the main motivations for independent education is the desire for something new, unknown, which is related to external stimulation and internal qualities of the individual. The ability to usefully implement the experience gained in the labor market and the ability to think creatively are the main incentives for creative assimilation of knowledge; Another incentive is the need to understand the objective reality more deeply and, of course, to understand that the knowledge acquired by students is the basis of social, personal and professional development.

Table 1

Indicators of independent education

Criteria	Signs	Indicators
Manifestation of creativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emergence of interest in learning; - Formation of mental abilities 	Interest in learning, imagination, activity in games, reading, drawing, etc
The need for self-awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-development ability; - Taking advantage of their opportunities 	Activating thought processes, this is a manifestation of age-appropriate interest
Pursuit of systematic independent education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High level of self-awareness - Determining the level of future activity, preparation and duration 	Determining methods of achieving the final result based on personal interests
Manifestation of creative thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transforming acquired knowledge into new views, ideas, imaginations; - High probability operation 	Independence in the selection and acquisition of knowledge, high efficiency in the acquisition of new material
Manifestation of creative activity	Determining the future activity, its size and duration of preparation	Making practical decisions
Improving the system of individual knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training planning; - Determining ways and means of achieving the goal 	Increasing the efficiency of independent educational activities
Development of motives for future independent activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Future spiritual development; - Formation of emotional and freedom qualities 	The influence of knowledge on the comprehensive development of the personality

Self-awareness in a reproductive form (repeating the material learned, completing tasks, etc.) is the first level of the process of creative learning and mastering. A high level of creative independence is the combination of previously learned and new material. The second stage is characterized by a high level of independence, the selected material is connected and restored with new methods of processing and analyzing the received information. The next, higher level of creative independence is determined by the student's ability to solve tasks, acquire new knowledge and acquire new skills using convenient methods of information search, selection and learning. The highest level of independent education is defined by independent formulation of problems and striving to solve them independently. The first two levels must be mastered to reach the last level. Creative thinking is also part of the process of acquiring sustainable skills for independent work. Talent is required for the manifestation of creative thinking, the process of acquiring knowledge, studying an interesting problem is related to creativity and thinking, and creative thinking skills are formed [2].

The main criterion of independent education is the ability of students to plan their lessons. It is related to defining the purpose of their activity, ways and means of its implementation, and

planning personal affairs. When planning the scheme of the educational task, the sequence, the availability of certain labor tools, the organization of the workplace and the progress of the educational process are determined. Independent planning of such activities is carried out in three stages. The first, direction stage - the student's mind realizes, thinks and evaluates his possibilities, the appropriateness of achieving the goal. At this stage, there are opinions for and against the continuation of independent activity. If positive motives prevail, independent activity planning moves to the next stage - the stage of thinking about the conditions and state of future activities. At the last, third stage of planning, execution planning is carried out, that is, the activity system and the sequence of the task execution scheme are imagined [4]. Students' planning of their work is inextricably linked with the development of self-control skills, that is, control of the correctness of their actions, timely detection and prevention of deviations from the planned plan, regulation and correction of their actions, and the skills of achieving goals. Self-control is an important tool for independent performance of academic work [3].

The steady acquisition of self-control skills by students means that the individual has moved to a high-quality development stage. The development of self-control requires strong will, effort, determination, and ability to overcome difficulties, as a result, self-control is one of the most important conditions for cultivating positive qualities of a person, such as will and determination. Successful mastering of self-control skills allows students to increase self-confidence, high self-esteem, independence and high cognitive activity.

Summary

Based on the results of scientific research, independent education can be defined as follows: independent education is a systematic activity aimed at the formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications based on the independent mastering of educational material, assignments of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience. Independent works differ from each other depending on the didactic purpose, task, level of complexity, who they are intended for (individual or team). In the process of independent education, it is important that the selected topics are scientific, systematic, interesting, practical, and interdisciplinary, as well as creative in independent work and assignments. It is possible to achieve positive results if its theoretical, practical, scientific, methodical and pedagogical foundations are analyzed, effective forms and tools are selected. In this, coherence of the topic with practice, scientific and interesting learning materials, systematicity of topics, multifacetedness and interdependence of assignments and tasks play an important role. But most importantly, it is necessary to pay attention to the aspirations and interests of students in the organization of independent educational activities. It is desirable to ensure that students can apply the acquired knowledge in practice, that they participate in socially useful, propaganda-campaign work [14].

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